

EDUCATING ANALITIC THINKING FOR PROTECTION OF YOUNG PEOPLE FROM DESTRUCTIVE IDEAS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the emergence of the concept of interactive ethics, its specific features and its importance for today's position in the spiritual and moral development of young people.

In the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 with the No. 707, "On measures to further improve information security on the World Wide Web" prohibits:

- Encourage forcible change of the existing constitutional order and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- propaganda of war, violence and terrorism, as well as religious extremism, separatism and fundamentalism;
- disclosure of information that is a state secret or other secret protected by law;
- dissemination of information that incites national, racial, ethnic or religious hatred, as well as infringes on the honor and dignity of citizens or business reputation, and interferes with their privacy;
- promotion of drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors;

– Circumstances such as promoting pornography.

In a globalizing world, information plays an important role in international and interstate relations. That is, it can manifest itself in the life of the world community as both a positive and a negative force. In this sense, the countries with great potential in the technical field will have favorable conditions. It is because of this superiority that they can and do promote values, attitudes, ideas, thoughts that are in line with their personal interests. According to this, anti-globalization movements are emerging in many countries, which are refusing to create a single global harmonized information space. It should be noted that the anti-globalization movement itself is becoming increasingly global.

As noted by the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov: "Our people are kind, simple and trustworthy,

they trust what is said in the press, on television and on the radio”, he said. Information centers working against us from abroad will try to take advantage of this”. [1, 46-6].

As a result of the development of rapid information and communication technologies, the processes of globalization between different peoples and nations of the world are living on the basis of various ideological threats that could negatively affect the spirituality of all mankind, including our people.

Every thought that is said about the impact of the Internet on the minds of students who are always interested in innovation and various information has a great meaning. Some hackers, who are well aware of the students' interest in the Internet, are using this skillfully to escalate the “information attack”. “The current processes of globalization in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries have created unprecedented opportunities for the development of all mankind, all peoples and nations of the world, especially the younger generation. First of all, the advanced achievements of science and technology, modern information and communication technologies, in particular, the Internet, open the borders between different countries and regions, so today we all witness the undoubted contribution to the development of mutual cooperation and integration, - said the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov. - But it should not be overlooked that such achievements, which are a high and bright manifestation of human thinking, are also used as an ideological weapon in the pursuit of the selfish intentions of some political forces with great power and financial capabilities. To understand the

essence of such attempts to derail the consciousness of the people, especially the youth, the spiritual world, their long and lasting, negative consequences and preventing such threats is becoming increasingly important for today”. [2; 5-p].

In this regard, I should say as an example of the words of President Sh. Mirziyoyev: “I can not sleep at night thinking that young people are being deceived and wasting their lives,” he said. After all, only yesterday these young people were our blackbirds, one of our neighbors, one of our sons, one of our daughters or nephews! When did they go astray, when did entered such kind of ways? Why were we unaware? When and where did we make a mistake? When did our children fall into the hands of strangers? Why are they demon-possessed and have become enemies of their parents and their country?” [3] – such kind of word urges us all to think deeply.

While the information crisis is primarily aimed at young people, it is necessary to sharply eliminate the factors that shape the negative political views of this attack from a pedagogical and psychological point of view.

It is necessary to know and actively influence the motives of political processes and the issues of political education of the individual, the formation and development of immunity to information attacks. That is why our state pays great attention to the political and social activity of young people, the formation of their political, legal and ideological consciousness. [4; 148].

An information attack is a beneficial information effect on the mind of a person, a society, aimed at changing or stabilizing his or her behavior. The sources of information attack are diverse. Their

subjects may be the media, the Internet, non-governmental organizations, public organizations, foundations, ordinary books, films, sculptures, paintings, and so on. The object of an information attack is an individual or a social group, the state. In today's world, the improvement of social spheres, the increase in the intellectual level of people also requires the improvement of information attack mechanisms. Because, it is seen as a convenient and effective way to establish dominance over a particular society. In turn, the issue of information security is becoming more urgent, leading political and social institutions to pay more

attention to strengthening the spiritual world of citizens.

Since the manifestations of information attacks are diverse, it is necessary to study and analyze the potential of each of them and at the same time form immunity against them.

These types of threats seek to misrepresent a person's social consciousness and thus constitute a crowd that lacks identity. Information threats are also interpreted as information attacks and shape the person in the way they want and throw them into a whirlpool of problems. As a result, the social consciousness of citizens is poisoned and a social disease develops in society [5; 19-6.].

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